

AHLSTM: Attention-Enabled Hierarchical LSTM Autoencoder Framework for detecting GPS Spoofing Attacks in Autonomous Vehicles

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Abstract— Autonomous Vehicles (AVs) are vulnerable to Global Positioning System (GPS) spoofing attacks that involve manipulating signals to mislead navigation systems. The attention-Enabled Hierarchical Long Short-Term Memory Autoencoder Framework (AHLSTM) model is proposed to effectively identify and counteract the impact of GPS spoofing in autonomous vehicle systems. This model utilizes a dataset featuring legitimate GPS signals extracted from diverse locations, mimicking both moving and static AV scenarios. The dataset was obtained through a universal software radio peripheral unit configured as a GPS receiver. Extracting thirteen significant features from eight parallel channels across acquisition, tracking, and navigation decoding stages, the dataset encompasses both authentic and spoofed data. The AHLSTM model, employing multiple LSTM cells collaboratively to discern long-term dependencies in time-series sequences, showcases exceptional accuracy, attaining an impressive rate of 99.26% in detecting GPS spoofing attacks. Comparative analysis with benchmark TEXBAT dataset and the implementation of ensemble models underscore the AHLSTM model's superior performance in predicting spoofed data.

Keywords – Global Positioning System, Spoofing attack, long short-term memory (LSTM), Autoencoder, Cyber attack.

1. Introduction

The arrival of self-driving cars (AVs) has caused a paradigm shift in the automobile industry, promising safer and more efficient transportation. To navigate and make intelligent decisions, these vehicles rely largely on Global Positioning System (GPS) technology. This reliance on GPS, on the other hand, exposes autonomous vehicles to a new and increasing threat: GPS spoofing attacks [1]. In this article, will look at what GPS spoofing is, what it could mean for autonomous vehicles, and what steps are being taken to combat this growing threat. GPS spoofing is a malicious technique in which an attacker modifies GPS signals received by a device in order to offer misleading position information. Attackers may deceive GPS receivers into thinking they are in a different location than they are by broadcasting fake GPS signals. This can have serious consequences in the context of autonomous vehicles, as the vehicle's decision-making mechanisms rely heavily on correct location information. Cyber-attacks on AV are classified into three types: data interception, data modification, and denial of service [2]. Civilian GPS signals were found to be unencrypted, making them susceptible to GPS spoofing and jamming. Because the attacker can redirect the AV route without noticed. GPS spoofing is considered most hazardous sort of cyber attack targeting AV.

Several articles presented artificial intelligence-based GPS spoofing detection systems. Varma et al.(2020)[3] suggested a computer architecture that detects spoofing and meaconing attacks using a neural network. When an attack is detected, the computer uses the Bayesian inference subsystem to assess its severity. TalaeiKhoei et al.(2022)[4] presented a system that is developed by machine learning models with a K-fold analysis, with voting mechanisms incorporated to select the learning model with high accuracy. Dependent on gyroscope measurements and GPS data, the scientists showed a straightforward method for detecting hijacking. Psiaki et al. (2016) [5] added a GPS spoofing detection and estimation system with switching mode resilience. The authors attempted to handle sensor drift by maintaining estimation errors in a tolerable zone with a high likelihood. Jiang et al. (2022) [6] introduce Deep POSE, a unique framework for detecting GPS spoofing attempts. Deep POSE is made up of spoofing detector and a vehicle position estimator. The vehicle position estimator uses the convolutional network with RNN to extract the vehicle direction and speed from the motion sensor data. To identify GPS spoofing attacks, spoofing detector compares this trajectory to one rebuilt from user-reported GPS coordinates. Wei, X et

al.(2022) [7] offers a unique machine learning (ML) model for distinguishing between faked and legitimate signals received by unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs). Multiple machine learning approaches are utilized to determine best classification technique, with GPS signal properties serving as features. K-fold analyses and varied K values are used to construct various ML models for improved accuracy. Fayha et al. (2023) [8] presented a new transformer-based model uses traditional and advanced DL techniques to detect and mitigate GPS spoofing attacks on phasor measurement units. The model includes a BLSTM in the encoder with decoder, outperforms statistical methods in correction accuracy and system size. It also outperforms statistical methods in real-time applications, demonstrating its potential for real-time applications. E. Shafiee et al. (2017) [9] address the vulnerability of civilian GPS signals to spoofing, deliberate interference leading to the acquisition of invalid navigation data. The study proposes a novel technique for GPS spoofing detection using features extracted from signal patterns, specifically early-late phase, delta, signal level. The author employs ML approaches, including K-NN and naive Bayesian classifiers, as well as a multi-layer neural network to achieve accurate and timely spoofing detection, as demonstrated through simulation results on a software GPS receiver. Quan Sun et al. (2021) [10] address security concerns in heterogeneous wireless communication, focusing on cross-technology communication (CTC) spoofing attacks, specifically from Wi-Fi to ZigBee devices. They propose a ML-based technique utilizing received signal strength (RSS) data to construct one-class support vector machine classifier for identifying CTC spoofing attacks. Through live test bed simulations, the results demonstrate the high effectiveness of the approach, achieving over 90% detection rate and precision, even at close distances (less than 2 m) with a limited number of samples. Ottosen et al. (2019) [11] developed two anomaly detection methods using k-NN and Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) in low-cost air quality dataset. They employed an absolute measurement of the residual to identify contextual anomalies and the average Euclid distance to identify point abnormalities. Using K-means clustering, both anomalies were categorized as normal and anomalous. Hossain et al. (2021) [12] suggested a hybrid prediction technique combining GRU and LSTM versions of the RNN model. The model outperformed a single GRU or LSTM model in terms of overall performance and tracked real AQI trends. Li et al. (2021)[13] presented a clustering-based fuzzy C-means algorithm for the PSO (particle swarm optimization) technique that uses reconstruction error and a reconstruction criterion as fitness functions. Unfortunately, because of the PSO method trap in local optima, the algorithm is unable to disclose the framework of highly dimensional multivariate time series. Jung et al. (2021) [14] used LSTM to predict indoor space conditions using 3 IoT sensor dataset measuring temperature, brightness, humidity. The method detects anomalous conditions where the readings from the datasets deviate from a training threshold, aiding facility management. Park et al. (2018) [15] developed a hybrid LSTM-VAE model to detect multimodal anomalies in robot-assisted feeding systems for people with disabilities. They analyzed data from 155 systems and found anomalous behaviours by calculating a reconstruction score based on task execution state. The model's ROC curve resulted in higher results than other similar approaches, demonstrating its potential for improving robot-assisted feeding systems. Zhou et al. (2020)[16] proposed Variational LSTM to address higher-dimensional anomaly problems in intelligent industrial applications. The VLSTM consists of an LSTM encoder, variational part, and decoder, reducing high-dimensionality input data and using variational Bayes for re-parameterization. R.Reka et al [17] proposes a novel intrusion detection system (IDS) for mobile ad hoc networks (MANETs) that uses a Centrality Coati Optimization Algorithm (COA) to form compact clusters and optimize cluster head selection. This system focuses on solving the issues of node mobility and energy consumption in MANETs, while a Multi-head Self-Attention based Gated Graph Convolutional Network (MSA-GCNN) identifies multiple types of attacks, such as DoS and Zero-Day. The approach aims to improve attack detection rates, reduce memory usage, and minimize computational overhead compared to existing methods.

Existing solutions for detecting GPS spoofing attacks in autonomous vehicles confront numerous problems. These include insufficient coverage of various spoofing techniques such as replay assaults, signal nulling, and fake data injection, limiting their effectiveness in real-world applications. Many systems use static thresholds or heuristic algorithms, which result in significant false positive and negative rates. They also fail to take full advantage of temporal dependencies in GPS signal data, making it harder to detect sophisticated attack patterns. Furthermore, computational inefficiency and resource-intensive models limit their usefulness for real-time detection in autonomous systems. The lack of interpretability in most models further limits their use in safety-critical applications. To overcome these issues, this study proposed the Attention-Enabled Hierarchical Long Short-Term Memory Autoencoder Framework as a solution to these problems. AHLSTM improves GPS spoofing detection performance by leveraging attention processes and numerous LSTM cells to describe long-term dependencies in time-series data. These are motivated us to do this research work.

The Novelty of this study introduces the Attention-Enabled Hierarchical Long Short-Term Memory Autoencoder Framework, which combines attention mechanisms with numerous LSTM cells to capture long-term dependencies within time-series GPS data. Unlike previous approaches, AHLSTM uses multi-channel feature extraction from multiple GPS signals, which improves its robustness and accuracy in detecting subtle spoofing attacks in a variety of dynamic situations. This method dramatically enhances detection performance, with a high accuracy rate in real-world AV circumstances.

The paper's contributions are as follows:

- The proposed AHLSTM model uses multiple Long Short Term Memory units to learn long-term data correlation with a GPS-spoofed data sequence. According to reconstruction error rates, the autoencoder chooses the optimum threshold to detect GPS-spoofed data.
- A Spearman's Correlation Coefficient method is used detect correlated and low-importance features simultaneously.
- The AHLSTM model proposes a self-attention mechanism for efficiently recognizing GPS spoofing data. Experimental results show that proposed model effectively detects GPS Spoofed data with an accuracy of 99.26\% based on comprehensive evaluation criteria.
- AHLSTM model is analyzed using a benchmark TEXBAT dataset.
- It evaluates the effectiveness of proposed method by employing, comparing, examining traditional ML-DL methods for performance validation.

2. Background Study

2.1 LSTM

The LSTM [18] is a form of RNN architecture designed to address the vanishing gradient problem with capture prolonged dependencies within sequential data. It incorporates memory cells with a sophisticated gating mechanism to regulate information flow. The Forget Gate decides that information from the previous cell state to discard, Input Gate determines the novel data to store, Output Gate controls the output information. Figure 1 illustrates the workings of the LSTM model.

Fig. 1. Working of LSTM Unit

- *Forget Gate (f_t)* - In a LSTM network, it determines that information from the previous cell state to discard or forget. It takes as input previous hidden state h_{t-1} , current input y_t , processes them through a weighted sum, applies the sigmoid activation function σ and produces an output between 0 and 1. This output element-wise multiplies with the previous cell state, effectively determining what information to retain or forget.

$$f_t = \sigma(w_f[h_{t-1}, Y_t] + b_f) \quad (1)$$

- *Input Gate (i_t)* - The cell state determines what new information \tilde{C}_t should be stored. Similar to forget gate, it takes previous hidden state, current input, processes them, and produces output between 0 and 1 utilizing sigmoid activation function. It also calculates a candidate cell state \tilde{C}_t using tanh activation function. The output and candidate cell state are then combined to update current cell state C_t .

$$i_t = \sigma(w_i[h_{t-1}, Y_t] + b_i) \quad (2)$$

$$\tilde{C}_t = \tanh(w_c[h_{t-1}, Y_t] + b_c) \quad (3)$$

- **Output Gate (o_t)** - It plays a important role in deciding which information to extract from the present hidden state h_t . By processing both prior hidden state and current input, the system generates an output ranging from 0 to 1 using sigmoid activation function. Simultaneously, tanh activation function processes the current state. Then current hidden state is then produced by combining these processed elements through the output gate.

$$o_t = \sigma(w_o[h_{t-1}, Y_t] + b_o) \quad (4)$$

$$h_t = o_t \odot \tanh(C_t) \quad (5)$$

2.2 Autoencoder

The Autoencoder, a neural network architecture, is utilized for discovering the structure of datasets and creating a compressed representation of input data [19]. To analyze data characteristics and extract features or patterns, the encoder transforms input data, generating lower-dimensional representation known as bottleneck layer. Subsequently, decoder reversely transforms the encoder, reconstructing the input signal as closely as possible to its original dimension. By eliminating irrelevant features, the encoding method converts a higher-dimensional vector into low-dimensional bottleneck layer representation (h), expressed as follows:

$$h = (f_1[w_i, x] + b_i) \quad (6)$$

The weight matrix w_i bias b_i and activation function f_1 are all crucial elements in determining the overall performance of a system. The decoding process utilizes the intermediate layer representation (h) to generate an output \hat{y} Equation (7) shows going back to the restoration of \hat{y} .

$$\hat{y} = (f_2[w_i, h] + b_j) \quad (7)$$

The decoder's activation function, weight matrix w_j , bias b_j and input sample \hat{y} are all crucial elements in the process. In order to reduce output-input discrepancies, the autoencoder model computes a reconstruction loss (L), which is frequently utilized for GPS-Spoofed data detection applications.

$$L(y - \hat{y}) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{n=1}^n |\hat{y}_t - y_t| \quad (8)$$

The input data is denoted by y, the output data is represented by \hat{y} , and the training dataset has n samples. In AHLSTM model, a calculation of a sample's reconstruction loss is expanded as follows:

$$y_i = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{n=1}^n |\hat{y}_i - y_i| \quad (9)$$

The reconstruction loss is computed for all samples using the following method.

$$RLOSS = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{N=i}^1 y_i \quad (10)$$

3. Proposed Methodology

3.1 System model

Fig. 2. A system model for detection of GPS spoofing attack in autonomous vehicle

In Fig. 2, the target car in green follows a predetermined path to reach its destination. Before the car arrives at the intersection area, a hacker broadcasts the GPS spoofing signals using an antenna. The spoofed car, which is in red, will redefine its present location based upon the GPS-spoofed signals. So, the car moves to left side of the road because the spoofed signal strength is more effective than legitimate signal that is received from the GPS satellites. An AHLSTM model is designed to identify GPS spoofing attacks in their early stages. The signal data is first gathered from the GPS receiver in the car, then analyzed, and specific features are retrieved. The features are fed into AHLSTM method to be further analyzed. When the pre-trained model detects an attack pattern, it immediately alerts the users. If the received signal is legitimate, the system will continue to operate.

3.2 AHLSTM-Attention-Enabled Hierarchical LSTM Auto encoder Framework

The study proposes a deep AHLSTM framework with a hierarchical attention mechanism for detecting GPS spoofing attacks in autonomous vehicles. The model consists of six steps: Import GPS time-series sequence Data, LSTM Encoders, Self-attention hierarchical block, LSTM Decoder Mechanism, GPS Spoofing detection, Reconstruction loss calculation.

Fig. 3. Proposed AHLSTM model

Fig. 3 is the outline of the proposed AHLSTM model, which blends characteristics from autoencoders and LSTM neural networks. Using LSTM memory cells, the encoder converts highly dimensional data input sequences into fixed-size vectors while maintaining associations between points of data and gradually reducing the input vector's dimensionality till it gets close to the latent space. This threshold serves as a decisive criterion for detecting anomalies indicative of GPS-spoofing incidents. Next, the LSTM decoder detects GPS spoofing attacks by using a threshold determined through reconstruction error rates. It accomplishes this by reproducing the input data patterns from the reduced form in latent space. This dual functionality of LSTM decoder not only ensures the identification of potential threats but also enables the faithful reconstruction of legitimate

GPS time-series data, providing a robust defence mechanism against malicious spoofing activities.

- **Step 1: Import GPS time-series sequence Data**

The original dataset is composed of time sequences $[y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n]$. The first step in the model involves creating input sequences from the GPS spoofing dataset. It constructs every sequence with fixed T-length time window data, where each data point, denoted as y_t , contains m-features at specific timestamps t. Then reshape these sequences into a 2-dimensional array format that includes samples and timestamps, preparing them for the LSTM encoder.

- **Step 2 :Functionality of LSTM Encoders – an Efficient Sequential Pattern Learning**

The Long Short Term Memory encoder functions as sequence folding layer, converting feature sequences into a batch of time-dependent feature sequences. The LSTM Encoder is useful in detecting GPS spoofing because it analyzes sequential GPS data and detects temporal patterns indicative of spoofing attacks. As input, the LSTM encoder obtains a sequence of GPS data points. Each data point should typically have the following information: latitude, longitude, altitude, and a timestamp. The resulting sequences have been processed and normalized before being given into the model. The LSTM encoder is composed of several LSTM layers stacked on top of one another. Each LSTM layer analyzes input sequence sequentially, just one step at a time. The LSTM Encoder describes pre-processing and encoding steps for this GPS spoofing time series dataset, specifically focused on GPS readings collected over 10 timestamps, each with 10 samples. The timestamps are represented in one dimension of the two-dimensional format created from the one-dimensional dataset, and the other represents the features (GPS readings). This reshaped dataset is then fed into an encoder. The encoder, consisting of Long Short Term Memory network with 10 LSTM cells, processes every sample in a sequential manner. Each LSTM cell decides whether to retain the forgotten information from the previous LSTM cell. The last LSTM cell accumulates information from all previous cells, resulting in a 1 x 16 vector representing encoded features. Additionally, Repeat Vector layer is introduced to create copies of this vector equal to number of timestamps (10 in this case), yielding a two-dimensional vector of 10 x 16, which is used for subsequent processing.

- **Step 3 :Self-attention hierarchical block**

In this paper, introduce a novel self-attention hierarchical block into the LSTM autoencoder model to understand the connection between genuine and manipulated GPS signals. The attention mechanism selectively emphasis on particular parts of input sequence, which differs from the typical LSTM model that relies on past hidden states and current information, leading to suboptimal performance. In sequence models, the attention mechanism enables encoders to generate a context vector specific to sequence portions. This ensures the representation of crucial elements and facilitates the learning of long-term dependencies, leading to improved decoder outputs. Additionally, it utilizes the encoder's hidden state information to calculate attention weights. At every time step, use (RV_{z1}) as the input to the LSTM, and set initial hidden vector as (h_0) . The colored box near the Long Short Term Memory unit at each time step represents hidden state, with colour length indicating amount of information obtained. In Figure 4, the output at the last layer ($t = 3$) shows a strong connection compared to the input of the second layer (RV_{z2}) . The last layer's hidden state in the attention block includes input information from the third and fourth layers of timestamps, leading to an inaccurate representation and poor decoder output. The substantial dependence of the output of the last layer upon at $(t = 2)$ is well captured by this attention approach. Therefore, the second layer is given more weight, resulting in improved decoder inputs and output sequences.

Fig.4. Comparison of Input sequence to decoder in case of a) Without attention, b) With attention in sequence utilizing AHLSTM

- **Step 4 :LSTM Decoder Mechanism for Sequential Output Generation**

The attention block's output serves as the input for the LSTM decoder, which receives a feature representation capturing spatial and temporal patterns. The decoder consists of one or more LSTM layers that sequentially process this feature representation. In contrast to typical sequence-to-sequence tasks where the decoder produces an output sequence, its role here is to reconstruct the original input sequence. Functioning as a layer for unfolding sequences, the LSTM decoder reconstructs the original sequence structure of the input data, which underwent reshaping during the encoding phase. The encoder produces 1 x 16 encoded feature sets, and these are directed into the decoder, specifically Layer 3, which consists of ten LSTM units. Every LSTM layer cell utilizes an encoded sample, generating an output that encapsulates the acquired knowledge from the encoded feature. This output undergoes multiplication with a 1 x 16 vector from an additional time distribution layer. Concurrently, each Long Short Term Memory cell unit generates second output containing processed state information, forwarding it to subsequent Long Short Term Memory LSTM cell, with exception of last unit. Importantly, multiplication of matrix occurs between each Long Short Term Memory layer's output and the Time Distribution layer, resulting in a 10 x 1 vector, matching the input sequence size and effectively restoring the original sequence structure. In each time step, the LSTM decoder uses tprevious time step's output and hidden state. The decoder's hidden state and output are employed at each step to reconstruct GPS sequence elements like latitude, longitude, altitude, or timestamp. At every time step, the decoder output is compared to the corresponding part of the original GPS sequence. Anomaly detection techniques can be applied to analyze dissimilarities between expected and actual data. The LSTM decoder's output layer predicts the next element in the GPS sequence. The accuracy of the LSTM decoder is assessed by comparing its output at each time step with the real value and its ability to faithfully reconstruct the input sequence.

- **Step 5 : GPS Spoofing detection**

For identifying GPS-spoofed data, a decision point is established by setting a threshold that determines the permissible deviation for spoofing data. Any spoofing data surpassing this threshold is categorized as an anomaly. The described anomaly detection technique involves training the model with a dataset containing GPS sequences falling within a normal range. Throughout the training process, the model computes reconstruction error rates associated with normal GPS sequences. The optimum reconstruction level of error becomes the optimum threshold after the training period. During the testing phase, a GPS spoofing dataset with varying ranges is input. The model computes the reconstruction error rate for all value in testing set, and if it exceeds the threshold, the corresponding sample is flagged as an anomaly. This threshold-based approach empowers the model to identify anomalies in GPS readings based on learned patterns from the training dataset.

- **Step 6 : Reconstruction loss Calculation**

In this section, compute reconstruction loss per each sample in each timestamps sequence. Assume the following 5 samples $[y_1, y_2, y_3, y_4, y_5]$ that are made up of three time-series data sequences of $[Y_1, Y_2, Y_3]$ with each sequence including three samples on three separate timestamps where $Y_1 \in [y_1, y_2, y_3]$, $Y_2 \in [y_2, y_3, y_4]$, $Y_3 \in [y_3, y_4, y_5]$. The proposed model uses such 3 time-series of GPS sequences as inputs with creates outputs that map to all sequence $\hat{Y}_1 \in [\hat{y}_1, \hat{y}_2, \hat{y}_3]$, $\hat{Y}_2 \in [\hat{y}_2, \hat{y}_3, \hat{y}_4]$

, $\hat{Y}_3 \in [\hat{y}_3, \hat{y}_4, \hat{y}_5]$.

Assume that the three sequences' initial values were as follows:

$Y_1 \in [y_1 = 1, y_2 = 2, y_3 = 3]$, $Y_2 \in [y_2 = 2, y_3 = 3, y_4 = 4]$, $Y_3 \in [y_3 = 3, y_4 = 4, y_5 = 5]$ where each timestamps mapping outputs were obtained as

$\hat{Y}_1 \in [\hat{y}_1 = 1.2, \hat{y}_2 = 2.03, \hat{y}_3 = 3.04]$, $\hat{Y}_2 \in [\hat{y}_2 = 1.79, \hat{y}_3 = 2.79, \hat{y}_4 = 3.69]$,

$\hat{Y}_3 \in [\hat{y}_3 = 3.03, \hat{y}_4 = 4.11, \hat{y}_5 = 5.03]$.

For each sample, the reconstruction loss can be estimated as follows:

$$y_1 = \frac{|1.2 - 1|}{1} = 0.2$$

$$y_2 = \frac{|2.03 - 2| + |1.79 - 2|}{2} = 0.12$$

$$y_3 = \frac{|3.04 - 3| + |2.79 - 3| + |3.03 - 3|}{3} = 0.09$$

$$y_4 = \frac{|3.69 - 4| + |4.11 - 4|}{2} = 0.2$$

$$y_5 = \frac{|5.03 - 5|}{1} = 0.03$$

A threshold, 0.2, is used to establish the maximum reconstruction error. Any sample that has a reconstruction error greater than 0.2 during validation is now labelled as a GPS-spoofing sequence.

3.3 Proposed Algorithm

The training phase of the proposed framework seeks to reduce reconstruction error and determine the optimum threshold for detection in the test phase. To ensure close alignment between outputs and inputs, the model minimizes reconstruction loss by determining the standard error rate for reconstructing GPS data points within normal range. In the testing phase, utilize this threshold to identify any anomalies or GPS-spoofing sequences in the test data set.

3.3.1 Training Stage

As outlined in Fig.5, Algorithm Stage 1, involving the reshaping of the original dataset into time-series sequences, converting the raw dataset to these GPS sequences is the first step in the training phases. Within the training dataset, each dataset y_i constitutes a sequence, wherein each sequence in the model consists of 10 GPS samples distributed across 10 timestamps. A GPS sample is a data point that contains basic GPS signal properties and represents positional information at a certain moment. Process 10 GPS samples scattered over 10 consecutive timestamps, with each sample capturing the GPS signal at a single timestamp. These samples are fed into the AHLSTM model as a time-series sequence. The hierarchical and self-attention processes use the temporal dependencies and patterns in these sequences to efficiently detect possible threats. To detect attacks, the model processes ten consecutive GPS samples. The detection relies on difference in reconstruction error between original and recreated GPS signals. If only a subset of the packets is spoofed, the model still detects the attack, depending on the degree of the spoofing. The output is a detection decision that indicates whether an attack exists in the sequence. Moving to Stage 2 : AHLSTM training within the algorithm, training of the method commences by sequentially presenting every sequence to encoder. A single Long Short Term Memory processes each sample in the sequence separately. The decoder constructs an LSTM network with cells corresponding to timestamps, handling each encoded feature through a single LSTM cell. The time-distributed dense layer produces the results, which are then reconstructed using reconstruction loss measured between output and input. The model continues training on timestamp sequences until reconstruction error is reduced for each samples. The encoder's latent space utilizes 16 neurons, 'tanh' as the activation function, two dropout layers, a repeat vector layer, and an additional time-distributed density layer. In Stage 3, set the maximum reconstruction error as optimum threshold. The modification of model's weights, parameters involves utilizing a back propagation technique and Mean Absolute Error (MAE) algorithm.

$$Loss(MAE) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i|}{n} \quad (11)$$

Here, n represents the total count of samples, where y_i stands for the initial input sent to encoder, \hat{y}_i signifies output acquired from the decoder.

3.3.2 Testing Stage -In Stage 4, outline the testing phase details of the proposed model, with a focus on detecting anomalies or GPS spoofing in the testing set. The previously trained LSTM encoder processed a sequence of 10 data points with 10 timestamps, encompassing all GPS values, resulting in the generation of an encoded and reduced feature representation. This representation is then used to create a single time series, and compare the resulting reconstruction error rate against a predefined threshold. If the reconstruction loss exceeds the threshold, categorize the respective data point as either an anomaly or GPS spoofing data; otherwise, it is considered legitimate data.

$$Y' = \begin{cases} Y'_i \text{ is GPS spoofing data,} & \text{if } l_{test_arr}[i] > \eta \\ Y'_i \text{ is legitimate data,} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Here, Y' represents a reconstructed time-series, Y'_i denotes an individual data point within the time-series, and $l_{testarr}[i]$ corresponds to the result of applying a reconstruction loss function based on Mean Absolute Error (MAE).

<i>Algorithm: AHLSTM-Attention-Enabled Hierarchical LSTM Auto encoder Framework</i>		
<p>Import GPS time-series sequence Data:</p> <p>Input: Training set $\{y_0, y_1, y_2, \dots, y_{n-1}\}$, Test set $\{y'_0, y'_1, y'_2, \dots, y'_{m-1}\}$, Timestamps t Output: A Set of GPS spoofing data (S_t) or legitimate data (L_t)</p> <p>begin</p> <p style="padding-left: 20px;">*Stage 1: To input sequence*</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;">Y_t, Y'_t: sets of training and testing data based on timestamps ($t = 10$)</p> <p style="padding-left: 20px;">for $i \in [0, n-t]$ do $Y_i = [y_t : y_{i+t}]$ end</p> <p style="padding-left: 20px;">for $i \in [0, m-t]$ do $Y'_i = [y'_i : y'_{i+1}]$ end</p>	<p>*Stage 2: AHLSTM training phase*</p> <p>Initialize the parameter of AHLSTM model</p> <p>for $Y_i \in [Y_0, Y_1, \dots, Y_{n-t}]$ do $\hat{Y}_i = M(Y_i)$ $L_{err} = \sum Y_i - \hat{Y}_i$ Update AHLSTM model to minimize L_{err} by Eq.8 end</p> <p>*Stage 3: Threshold setting*</p> <p>Function Reconstruction Loss (Y): Y_i reconstruction error calculation:</p> <p style="padding-left: 20px;">for $i \in (0, n-t)$ do $\hat{Y}_i = M(Y_i)$ $Err_{arr}[i, i : i+t] = \hat{Y}_i - Y_i$ end</p> <p>End Function</p>	<p>*Calculation of all data Reconstruction errors*</p> <p>for $i \in (0, n)$ do $l_{test_arr}[i] = \sum Err_{arr}[:, i] / \sum (Err_{arr}[:, i] - 0)$ end</p> <p>return l_{test_arr}</p> <p>/ Max Reconstruction Loss from training dataset / threshold</p> <p>$(\eta) = \max(RLOSS(Y_0, Y_1, \dots, Y_{n-t}))$</p> <p>*Stage 4: GPS Spoofing detection on testing set*</p> <p>$l_{test_arr} = RLOSS(Y'_0, Y'_1, \dots, Y'_{m-t})$</p> <p>for $i \in (0, m)$ do if $l_{test_arr}[i] > \eta$ then $y'_i \rightarrow S_t$ else $y'_i \rightarrow L_t$ end end end</p>

Fig.5. Algorithm: AHLSTM-Attention-Enabled Hierarchical LSTM Auto encoder Framework.

4. Experiments

4.1 Dataset description

The dataset contains of a collection of Global Positioning System (GPS) signals, including both authentic and spoofed samples. The authentic signals represent normal behaviour, while the spoofed samples are used to simulate GPS spoofing attacks for detection purposes. These legitimate signals, collected from different locations, were used to simulate both moving and static autonomous vehicle scenarios [19]. The proposed AHLSTM framework is specifically trained and verified on GPS data, hence its performance may be closely related to GPS signal characteristics. For the solution to be useful in a worldwide setting, its adaptability to different GNSS systems must be assessed. This highlights the crucial necessity to examine if the properties retrieved from GPS signals are relevant and sufficient to detect spoofing attempts in other GNSS technologies, hence providing greater utility and adaptability. The dataset contains 158,170 samples, with 55% of legitimate instances and 45% corresponding to simulated GPS spoofing attacks. During data collection, thirteen features were extracted from eight-parallel channels at various receiver stages. This dataset was designed to investigate impact of GPS spoofing attacks on the extracted features and to develop detection techniques for such attacks using both supervised and unsupervised machine learning. The dataset is available in Excel format and includes a separate file with raw GPS data for simulating customized attacks. These features, extracted from both legitimate, spoofed GPS signals, utilized to develop techniques for detecting with categorizing spoofed and authentic GPS signals. The dataset can be divided into training, validation, and testing subsets. Typically, 70% of data is utilized for training, 15% for validation, 15% for testing. This ensures a balanced approach to model building, with training data utilized for learning, validation set for hyperparameter tuning, and testing set for final performance assessment. Stratified sampling can also be used to maintain a balance between real and spoofed instances.

4.2 Feature Description

The dataset includes several features extracted from authentic GPS signals collected from various locations. Here is a description of the features:

- *Satellite Vehicle Number (PRN)*: A unique number identifies each GPS satellite.
- *Carrier Doppler in Hz (DO)*: The frequency drift between transmitted and received GPS signal is caused by the motion of the satellite and receiver, resulting in the Doppler shift.
- *Pseudo-range in meter (PD)*: The pseudo-range is the time difference between transmission and reception of the GPS signal, expressed in meters, indicating a low level of fluency.
- *Receiver Time (RX)*: The receiver time is elapsed time in seconds since the start of the Time of the Week (TOW).
- *Time of the Week in seconds (TOW)*: TOW represents number of seconds that have elapsed since the start of the week, according to satellite atomic clock.
- *Carrier Phase Cycles (CP)*: CP, or carrier phase, represents frequency difference between received satellite signal's carrier and reference frequency generated by the receiver, measured in cycles.
- *Magnitude of Early Correlator (EC)*: EC denotes early correlator's magnitude in the correlation process.
- *Magnitude of Late Correlator (LC)*: The late correlator magnitude (LC) is represented by the line during the correlation process. These features are extracted at various stages of the GPS receiver, encompassing post-correlation, correlation, and pre-correlation.

4.3 Data Pre-processing

During the missing value detection stage, the dataset had been pre-processed by locating, eliminating any null value unknown and value noise [20]. Encoding any category values into numbers is the next step. The dataset contains just 2 categorical data values, which designate signals as either attack or normal. To do this, encode spoofed signals as 1 and legitimate signals as 0. The next step involves the application of normalization and standardization techniques to facilitate feature scalability. Additionally, rescaled result to mean of zero with standard deviation of one using an automatic standardization procedures.

4.4 Feature Selection method

A feature selection technique is used to increase the resilience of feature selection methods. The Spearman Correlation assesses the degree and direction of a monotonic relationship between two variables. It works especially well when the relationship between features is non-linear, making it appropriate for complex time-series data such as GPS signals. Because the Spearman Correlation works with ranking data, it is less sensitive to outliers, resulting in robust feature selection in noisy datasets like those containing GPS signals. By focusing on features with the highest monotonic correlation, the Spearman Correlator helps to reduce dimensionality while maintaining the framework's detection accuracy. It employs a heterogeneous

ensemble feature selection technique dependent on Spearman's correlation, information gain, two standard feature selection strategies. Spearman Correlation [21] computes the score τ given by: to determine the relationship and direction of each two features.

$$\tau = 1 - \frac{6 \sum_{i=1}^n (d_i)^2}{n(n^2-1)} \quad (13)$$

If a feature exhibits a coefficient exceeding 0.9, it indicates correlation. Consequently, we removed one feature from every pair of associated features. The Spearman correlation statistics reveal a score of 0.94 for the pairs ([TOW, RX], [DO, TCD]), signifying a strong correlation. This led to the elimination of RX and TCD functionalities. As expected, the RX serves as the receiver's reference time, TCD represents Doppler measurements in tracking blocks. In Fig. 6, illustrate outcomes from ensemble feature selection, utilizing Spearman's correlation. In the dataset, we removed correlated features with a coefficient above 0.9 and low-importance features with a score below 0.1. Notably, Fig. 6 reveals significant associations, with DO and TCD showing a 95% correlation and TOW and RX exhibiting a 94% correlation. Prioritizing features, DO takes precedence over TCD and TOW over RX, leading to the exclusion of TCD and RX from the dataset for GPS signal categorization.

Fig. 6 Spearman's Correlation heatmap

4.5 Hyper parameter Tuning

The Bayesian optimization method is recognized as most effective for this case. It may be used to maximize functions employing a relatively alternative model [22]. This method can provide durable solutions for optimizing black-box functions by simulating unknown functions with a non-parametric Gaussian process. Here, use Bayesian optimization for optimization tuning because of its merits and the inadequacies of other methodologies. This study utilizes Bayesian optimization for optimization tuning. By utilizing a non-parametric analysis using the Gaussian process, one may simulate unknown functions. The acquisition function, a surrogate utility function, is employed to enhance the optimality of the underlying function [23], highlighting the benefits and shortcomings of this approach.

4.6 Experiment Setup

The experiments are carried out utilizing following system setup given in Table 1

TABLE 1: Implementation environment specification

Unit	Description
Processor	AMD Ryzen 7 5800X
RAM	32GB
OS	Ubuntu 22.04 LTS
Packages used	PyTorch 1.10.0, scikit-learn 0.25.3

The hyper-parameters utilized in the training phase are demonstrated with values for all parameter along with description in Table II.

TABLE 2: AHLSTM Training Configuration

Hyper parameters	Values	Descriptions
Learning rate	0.002	Learning speed
Dropout	0.3	No. of neurons discarded during training
Batch size	128	No. of processed in a single forward/backward pass
Epoch	50	No. of one fwd/bwd pass of overall samples

5. Experimental Results and Comparative Analysis

It perform a comparative examination of AHLSTM model against the benchmark TEXBAT dataset. It employ state-of-the-art models, encompassing both ML-DL paradigms, to assess the performance of proposed AHLSTM method.

5.1 Evaluation Metrics

Accuracy in classification models reflects proportion of correctly predicted outcomes to total predictions, indicating model's accuracy. It is given in equation (14).

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \quad (14)$$

Precision measures the proportion of correctly predicted labels out of total predictions, with higher values indicating better accuracy and the precision is given in equation (15).

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad (15)$$

F1-Score, a statistical measure, combines machine learning model precision and recall into a single value by calculating harmonic mean, offering comprehensive evaluation that considers both precision, recall, penalizing extreme cases with significant differences between accuracy and recall in the confusion matrix. It is given in equation (16).

$$F1 - \text{score} = 2 \times \left(\frac{\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \right) \quad (16)$$

Probability of Detection measures the ability of methods to correctly detect GPS spoofed data. A high Probability of Detection indicates that the model is effective at identifying instances of spoofed data. Probability of Detection is formulated in equation (17).

$$\text{Probability of Detection} = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (17)$$

Probability of Misdetection measures the rate at which the model fails to detect GPS spoofed data. A low Probability of Misdetection indicates that the model is less likely to miss instances of spoofed data. Then, the probability of Misdetection is given in equation (18).

$$\text{Probability of Misdetection} = \frac{FN}{TP+FN} \quad (18)$$

Probability of False Alarm- This metric measures the rate at which method incorrectly classifies GPS spoofed data as legitimate data. A low Probability of False Alarm indicates that the model is less prone to incorrectly classifying GPS spoofed data as legitimate data. Then, it is given in equation (19).

$$\text{Probability of False Alarm} = \frac{FP}{TN+FP} \quad (19)$$

5.2 Proposed AHLSTM Model Evaluation Results

To evaluate the performance of LSTM encoder-based GPS spoofing detection model, it used a real-world GPS dataset consisting of both legitimate and spoofed GPS data. The dataset was collected from various sources, including GPS receivers and simulated spoofing attacks. The proposed model is trained using all training datasets at each epoch, and its performance is assessed on a validation set. According to Fig. 7, training and testing accuracy and loss functions of the AH-LSTM method demonstrate that implementation of early stopping resulted in the model's validation error failing to improve beyond epoch 49, indicating that the model had reached its optimal performance and training was halted. According to the AH-LSTM model's performance metrics, it achieved an accuracy of approximately 99.26%.

Fig.7. Training/Validation accuracy and Loss function of AHLSTM model

In Fig.8, by applying the threshold, it can simplify the task into a binary classification: If the reconstruction loss of a dataset falls below the threshold, categorize it as authentic GPS signal data. Conversely, if the loss surpasses the threshold, classify it as GPS-spoofed signal data.

Fig 8. Reconstruction loss – a)for legitimate GPS data b)for Spoofing GPS data

5.3 Model Evaluation: Analyzing Proposed Model Performance with Existing Dataset

This paper uses an ensemble method to test the efficiency of proposed methods. The various evaluation metrics that are used and compared with benchmark datasets are given in Table 3. It perform well in the GPS-spoofed dataset and the TEXBAT dataset [24]. The GPS-spoofed dataset is used in this AHLSTM model and has achieved better performance. Now, we are going to compare the proposed method with existing TEXBAT dataset. The TEXBAT dataset is a comprehensive collection designed for investigating GPS spoofing attacks. It comprises 158,170 samples, with 55\% representing legitimate instances and 45\% corresponding to three simulated GPS spoofing attack types—simplistic, intermediate, and sophisticated. Extracted from authentic GPS signals, the dataset includes 13 features from various receiver stages, capturing aspects like Doppler shift measurements and pseudo-range readings. With a focus on supervised and unsupervised machine learning, the TEXBAT dataset facilitates development of effective GPS spoofing detection methods by showcasing impact of spoofing attacks on GPS signal features.

TABLE 3. A Comparative Analysis: Evaluating a Proposed Model Against a Benchmark Dataset

Benchmark dataset	Existing Models	Precision	F1-Score
GPS spoofed dataset	AE	0.82	0.78
	LSTM-AE- Without Attention	0.86	0.82
	Proposed AH-LSTM- With Attention	0.93	0.91
TEXBAT dataset	AE	0.87	0.83
	LSTM-AE- Without Attention	0.93	0.87
	Proposed AH-LSTM- With Attention	0.98	0.93

In the evaluation of GPS spoofing detection methods on two dataset, GPS spoofed dataset and TEXBAT dataset, three distinct approaches were compared: the autoencoder (AE), LSTM autoencoder, attention-based hierarchical LSTM (AH-LSTM-Attention). The metrics used for assessment included precision, and F1-score. For the GPS-spoofed dataset, the AH-LSTM method demonstrated superior performance with a precision of 0.93, F1-score of 0.91, outperforming both AE and LSTM-AE. Similarly, on TEXBAT dataset, the AH-LSTM-Attention method continued to excel with a precision of 0.98, F1-Score of 0.93, surpassing the other two methods. These results suggest that the attention-based hierarchical LSTM method consistently outperforms traditional autoencoder and LSTM-AE approaches regards precision F1-score for GPS spoofing detection, making it a more effective model for this particular evaluation.

5.4 Comparative study with Machine Learning Models

It performed a comparative analysis of the AHLSTM model by employing various machine learning algorithms for model construction. This included traditional classifiers like One-Class SVM, Isolation Forest, Random Forest, and XGBoost. The efficacy of one-class SVM, Isolation Forest, Random Forest, XGBoost in predicting GPS-spoofed data depends on factors like feature representation and the adaptability of traditional machine learning models. However, the dynamic nature of GPS spoofing, evolving attack techniques, complex, non-linear relationships in data may make deep learning models like LSTMs advantageous for capturing intricate patterns and temporal dependencies. Experimenting with various models, feature representations, and pre-processing techniques is recommended to optimize performance for specific GPS spoofing detection tasks. The GPS signal spoofing detection machine learning model relies on hyper-parameters, whose manual selection is crucial for effective training. Poor choices may lead to over fitting or under fitting, impacting accuracy. Two common methods involve evaluating a range of hyper-parameters and fine-tuning them through empirical testing. Manual tuning takes a lot of time, though. It used the grid search approach to simplify this, methodically changing the hyper-parameters within predetermined ranges. Grid search sequentially modifies hyper-parameters, training models to identify the set yielding the highest accuracy. It is an efficient process of training and comparison.

5.5 Comparative study with Deep Learning Models

In Fig. 9, it evaluated the effectiveness of several neural network models, including the Variational Autoencoder (VAE), Autoencoder, LSTM networks [25], for GPS signal spoofing detection. These models were chosen for their potential to capture complex patterns inherent in GPS signals. Additionally, benchmarked their computational performance against the AH-LSTM method proposed .To maintain consistency in the evaluation process, kept the hyper parameter selection for the

VAE, Autoencoder, LSTM, and AH-LSTM models uniform. The comparison provides insights into the relative performance of each model in detecting GPS signal spoofing.

Fig 9. Accuracy and loss functions for VAE , AE, LSTM model.

It conducted a comprehensive evaluation of supervised ML methods for GPS signal spoofing using a GPS signal dataset. Employing techniques such as data augmentation, grid search, and validation, assessed the performance of seven selected models. The results are illustrated in Fig. 10, Comparative Analysis of State-of-the-Art Models Utilizing Performance Metrics on the GPS Spoofing Dataset. Notably, AH-LSTM method introduced in this investigation exhibited outstanding performance, attaining higher levels of accuracy, precision, F1-Score among the seven methods. Specifically, the AH-LSTM model yielded accuracy, precision, F1-score values of 0.9926, 0.9798, 0.9723, respectively. The proposed AH-LSTM method outperforms traditional machine learning models in GPS spoofing data detection. Deep learning models do better than

traditional models in four ways: they can automatically pick out important details from raw data, handle a lot of different data types, learn from start to finish, and achieve higher accuracy in detecting things. They also capture nonlinear relationships in spoofing data due to their multiple nonlinear layers. Both LSTM and VAE are tailored for sequential data processing, effectively addressing long-term dependencies and memory needs. Consequently, they prove to be adept at handling deceptive data characterized by sequential properties. Although LSTM boasts more intricate mechanisms for information regulation, sophisticated gating mechanisms, and advanced modelling capabilities in comparison to VAE, it frequently outperforms VAE in processing spoofing data. This superiority stems from LSTM's enhanced ability to capture and utilize features more effectively. The AH-LSTM model demonstrates superior computational performance in detecting AV GPS-spoofed data.

Fig 10.Comparative Analysis of State-of-the-Art Models Utilizing Performance Metrics on GPS Signal Spoofing Dataset

Fig 11. Latency Analysis

Figure 11 depicts latency illustrates that the proposed AHLSTM model reduced latency than VAE, AE, and normal LSTM for all input sequence lengths. This reduction is due to AHLSTM's optimized architecture, which includes attention techniques and hierarchical structures to speed up processing. The proposed approach decreases processing time by efficiently managing sequential input and minimizing redundant computations, making it ideal for real-time applications.

TABLE 4: Performance Analysis of proposed method with different Approaches

Methods	Performance Measures		
	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	F1-score (%)
Temporal Convolutional Network (TCN) [26]	89.56	90.28	87.34
TCN-LSTM [27]	93.45	92.78	93.78
AHLSTM (Proposed)	99.5	98.67	97.19

Table 4 compares the performance of various approaches according to accuracy, precision, F1-score. The proposed AH-LSTM model has the maximum performance, with 99.5% accuracy, 98.67% precision, and a 97.19% F1-score. TCN-LSTM performs moderately, outperforming the Temporal Convolutional Network (TCN) across all criteria. These results demonstrate the proposed AH-LSTM model's greater effectiveness in the specified task.

TABLE 5: Performance Analysis of proposed method with different Correlator Approaches

Methods	Performance Measures		
	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	F1-score (%)
Pearson correlation [28]	94.67	89.47	87.19
Sparse Canonical correlation [29]	92.36	90.29	89.65
AHLSTM (Proposed) using Spearman Correlation	99.5	98.67	97.19

Table 5 shows the proposed AHLSTM approach is compared to Pearson Correlation and Sparse Canonical Correlation in terms of detecting spoofing irregularities in GPS signals. The AHLSTM model performs much better than other techniques, with high accuracy (99.5%), precision (98.67%), F1-score (97.19%). This exhibits AHLSTM's exceptional ability to detect anomalies with few false positives and negatives. The improved performance is most likely owing to its sophisticated feature extraction and sequential learning capabilities, which are specifically tuned to GPS data properties.

TABLE 6: Comparison of Detection Performance Metrics with State-of-the-Art Models

Evaluation metrics	One Class-SVM	IF	VAE	AE	LSTM	RF	XGBoost	AHLSTM
Probability of Detection	95.26%	95.38%	92.87%	86.87%	94.68%	95.32%	96.23%	98.92%
Probability of Misdetction	4.74%	4.62%	7.13%	13.13%	5.32%	4.68%	3.77%	1.08%
Probability of False Alarm	4.29%	3.29%	5.74%	5.74%	3.86%	3.54%	3.43%	2.25%

Table 6 examines the detection performance of different ML methods for identifying GPS spoofing data. The Probability of Detection (True Positive Rate) demonstrates that models such as XGBoost (96.23%) and Isolation Forest (95.38%) perform well, with AHLSTM outperforming them all at 98.92%. The probability of misdetction (false negative rate) for AHLSTM is the lowest (1.08%), showing that it successfully reduces missed detections. In terms of False Alarm Rate (False Positive Rate), AHLSTM once again outperforms with a low value of 2.25%, demonstrating its ability to avoid misclassifying valid data as spoofed. Overall, AHLSTM outperforms in detecting spoofed data, with high detection rates, low misdetction and false alarm rates.

6. Conclusion

The propose an AH-LSTM model for the detection of GPS signal spoofing, leveraging an authentic dataset collected in a real-world environment using an Autonomous Vehicle and a deceptive spoofing jammer. Through an in-depth analysis employing Spearman's rank correlation coefficient, identified key features, reducing initial set from 65 to 15. The AHLSTM framework detects GPS spoofing attempts in autonomous vehicles using hierarchical LSTM, autoencoders, and an attention mechanism. By learning regular GPS patterns, it detects spoofing abnormalities as higher reconstruction mistakes. The attention mechanism aids in focusing on important data points. This method ensures real-time spoofing detection, allowing self-driving vehicles to maintain reliable navigation by switching to alternate sensors or techniques. Ultimately, it enhances the security and safety of autonomous vehicles by preventing misdirection caused by GPS manipulation. Hyper parameter tuning for machine learning algorithms (one-class SVM, Isolation Forest, Random Forest, and XGBoost) was performed using grid search, while neural network models (VAE, AE, LSTM, and AHLSTM) underwent training and testing with early stopping. The results highlight the AH-LSTM model's superior performance, achieving an impressive accuracy of 99.26%. In conclusion, the implementation of the AH-LSTM neural network demonstrates a robust GPS signal spoofing detection model, showcasing the potential of the AH-LSTM deep learning approach in countering GPS spoofing in AV. Looking ahead, future research aims to enhance computational efficiency and generalization capabilities by utilizing more intricate datasets as GPS signal inputs. This aims to decrease complexity while preserving computational efficiency, facilitating the model's deployment within Autonomous Vehicle (AV) systems. Additionally, ongoing research indicates a prevalent reliance on simpler DL fusion methods in existing AV GPS signal spoofing detection studies. In future research initiatives, goal is to propose deep neural network methods dependent on unique feature information present in GPS Spoofing data. This initiative seeks to overcome limitations and explore new possibilities in the field of GPS signal spoofing detection for Autonomous Vehicles. Future work will focus on extending the proposed method to other GNSS technologies, such as Galileo and Beidou, and evaluating the model on those signals. It will investigate system-specific aspects such as signal structure and noise patterns, as well as improve preprocessing and feature extraction stages, to ensure robustness and flexibility across a variety of GNSS systems.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this study.

Data availability

GPS Signal and TEXBAT are publicly available datasets.

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